

THE SOCIOECONOMIC BURDEN OF HEPATITIS B AND C IN PAKISTAN: A QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS

Sajjad^{*1}, Habib Ur Rahman², Misbah Nosheen³, Wasim FNU⁴, Muhammad Waqar⁵, Wafa Idrees⁶, Habiba Idrees⁷

^{*1,5}Genome Center for Excellence in Molecular Based Diagnostic and Research, Cl-25, Block-B Abdalian Housing Society, Lahore, Pakistan

²Department of medicine, Zia medical collage Mardan

³Department of Economics Hazara University, Mansehra, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan,

⁴Corewell Health William Beaumont University Hospital Royal Oak Michigan

⁶Khyber Medical College, Peshawar Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

⁷CMH Lahore Medical Collage, Lahore Cantt. Pakistan

¹mskhan_pu88@yahoo.com, ²habeeb1957@hotmail.com, ³misbah.nosheen@yahoo.com,

⁴waqarkhan96@gmail.com, ⁵drmwasi91@gmail.com, ⁶wafaidrees96@gmail.com, ⁷habibaidrees@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Sajjad

Abstract

Health is a fundamental asset that enables individuals to realize their full potential. When compromised, it leads to emotional, physical, and economic challenges that hinder human development. This study examines the socioeconomic impact of viral Hepatitis B and C in Pakistan, focusing on labor productivity, household income, morbidity, mortality, and the associated direct and indirect costs borne by patients and their families.

Primary data collected from 8,388 patients across 70 districts of Pakistan, including Azad Jammu and Kashmir and Gilgit Baltistan, through a structured questionnaire encompassing 36 demographic and economic indicators. Descriptive statistics, probit, logit, and OLS models were used to analyze the data.

Results indicate that Hepatitis B and C significantly reduce labor productivity through absenteeism and presenteeism, averaging 1.89 lost workdays per month per patient and attendant, with a total estimated annual loss of 32.43 million workdays nationwide. The diseases also affect labor mobility, with 2.07% visa rejections, 6.2% job rejections, 1.2% job terminations, and 5.2% mortality attributed to hepatitis. Additionally, income loss due to reduced work capacity and forced asset sales was observed.

The regression analysis provides compelling evidence that Hepatitis B and C have statistically significant and negative effects on key labor market outcomes in Pakistan. The models consistently indicate that individuals suffering from hepatitis experience reduced labor mobility, higher absenteeism rates, and an increased likelihood of job rejection. These findings persist even after controlling for demographic, socioeconomic, and regional factors, underscoring the direct burden of viral hepatitis on workforce participation and productivity.

Marginal effects further demonstrate the intensity of this impact, with hepatitis patients being significantly more prone to economic vulnerability, including the selling of assets to fund medical treatment. These dynamics highlight not only a health crisis

but also a labor market distortion that can exacerbate poverty and inequality, particularly in already marginalized communities. These findings underscore the need for policy reforms that protect infected individuals from discrimination and improve access to medical care, insurance, and job retention support

INTRODUCTION

Viral hepatitis—comprising types A, B, C, D, and E—affects millions globally and contributes significantly to both acute and chronic liver disease. It ranks as the 8th leading cause of death worldwide, responsible for approximately 1.41 million annual deaths, including those from liver cancer, cirrhosis, and acute infections. This burden is comparable to that of tuberculosis and HIV/AIDS. Of these fatalities, around 55% are linked to hepatitis B (HBV), 35% to hepatitis C (HCV), and the remainder to hepatitis A (HAV) and E (HEV). Hepatitis is also an increasing contributor to mortality among individuals living with HIV, with co-infection rates ranging from 5–20% for HBV and 5–15% for HCV.

Globally, an estimated 130–150 million individuals are living with HCV, while approximately 2.4 billion are infected with HBV. Without substantial global action, HBV infections are projected to remain at elevated levels for the next four to five decades, potentially leading to 20 million additional deaths between 2015 and 2030. This situation demands urgent international attention.

Pakistan bears the second-highest burden of HCV in the world, after Egypt. HBV and HCV significantly contribute to rising morbidity and mortality in the country. According to a 2017 Government of Punjab report, roughly one in every 13 Pakistanis is infected with either HBV or HCV.

A nationwide survey in 2008 estimated HBV prevalence at 2.5% and HCV at 5%. In Punjab, HCV prevalence was even higher, at 6.7%, while HBV stood at 2.4%. These rates suggest that approximately 8 million Pakistanis are infected with HCV and 4 million with HBV. A modeling study by the University of Bristol projected that Pakistan must treat around 1.1 million HCV cases annually to meet the World Health Organization's (WHO) 2030 hepatitis elimination target.

Contributing factors to the high incidence of hepatitis in Pakistan include unsafe blood transfusions (15%), hospitalization history (14%), dental procedures (13%), use of non-sterile injections (12%), surgical history (9%), sexual transmission, maternal transmission, lack of screening facilities, outdated sanitation systems, and unhygienic practices in barbershops.

On August 29, 2005, Pakistan launched its first national strategy to combat viral hepatitis, in collaboration with the Centre of Excellence in Molecular Biology (CEMB) at the University of the Punjab, Lahore. The initiative aimed to reduce hepatitis-related morbidity and mortality by leveraging the existing healthcare infrastructure. Between 2005 and 2010, the government allocated Rs. 2.59 billion to the program, while CEMB provided diagnostic services worth Rs. 113.6 million.

In 2005, Pakistan suffered an estimated \$1 billion loss in national income due to premature deaths from chronic diseases such as heart disease, stroke, and diabetes (WHO, 2005). The importance of health and education in human capital formation was emphasized by economists like Romer (1989) and Makin et al. (1980), building upon foundational work by Schultz (1961). Investments in health and education are now widely recognized as essential for enhancing employment, reducing poverty, accelerating economic growth, and improving individual capabilities in developing nations.

A strong correlation exists between health and income. Life cycle models (Smith 1998, 1999; Lillard & Weiss 1997) suggest that health status influences long-term income, consumption, and wealth. Sorkin (1997) confirmed the role of health in economic development via reduced mortality rates, particularly in developing countries.

Good health directly enhances labor productivity by increasing workers' capacity and reducing absenteeism. Jack (1999) emphasized that both

mental and physical well-being, along with human capital investments and effective labor management, shape productivity. Improved health also increases life expectancy and work experience, further boosting workforce quality.

The relationship between health and economic output is well-established. Healthy workers are more active, less frequently absent, and generally more productive. Poor health is a poverty trap, while better health leads to broader economic gains (WHO, 1999; World Bank, 1993). Barro (1996) viewed health as a productive capital asset essential for growth. WHO (2005) reported that about half the disparity in growth rates between developed and developing countries stems from differences in health and life expectancy.

High-income nations allocate significant budget portions to healthcare, acknowledging its central role in economic development. According to the UN (2019), spending 8–10% of GDP on health is recommended to drive sustainable economic growth.

Educational investments not only alleviate poverty but also reduce crime, terrorism, and income inequality (Faber & Augersaud, 2004). Household poverty tends to decline with improved education and health (Rodriguez et al., 2000). However, poverty also acts as a barrier to education, as financial hardships discourage school attendance. Modern firms are increasingly challenged by global economic pressures, aging workforces, and rising chronic disease burdens such as hepatitis, diabetes, and cardiovascular diseases. Unhealthy workers reduce productivity and increase operational costs. British health insurers project a future workforce with higher illness rates, including hepatitis and related conditions. Absenteeism and presenteeism are major concerns, with occupational health systems proving inadequate for current needs. The European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (2000) reported a loss of 600 million working days annually due to work-related illness in Europe.

Huisman et al. (2005) observed a 70% decline in productivity among workers with HCV. Younossi et al. (2016) found that HCV patients experienced 23.7% absenteeism and a 13% reduction in work-related performance. Yaseen et al. (2017) similarly

identified lower productivity in hepatitis patients in Faisalabad, Pakistan.

Hepatitis continues to be a pressing global health issue, particularly in developing countries such as Pakistan, Egypt, and others in South Asia (Glass et al., 2012). Globally, an estimated 130–150 million people are infected with HCV and 250 million with HBV (Issur et al., 2014). Hepatitis-related deaths (1.4 million annually) exceed those from malaria (1.2 million), tuberculosis (1.2 million), and rival those from HIV (1.5 million). Hepatitis B, C, and D are primarily transmitted through blood, body fluids, unsafe medical procedures, and vertical transmission, while HAV and HEV are spread through contaminated food and water. In Pakistan, an estimated 325 people die daily from viral hepatitis.

Unlike developed countries like the U.S. and those in Europe, where hepatitis-related deaths are well-documented, much of the world lacks comprehensive data on this public health crisis. WHO data show a strong association between HBV and HCV and increased mortality, especially in East and Southeast Asia, though these trends are often underreported (Wu et al., 2020).

Between 2003 and 2013, the U.S. experienced a rise in hepatitis-related deaths from 11,051 to 19,368 annually, an average increase of 865 deaths per year (Kathleen et al., 2016). In East and Southeast Asia, China had the highest hepatitis-related mortality until 2015, followed by Japan. Post-2015, Japan's rate exceeded China's, while declines were observed in the Philippines and Singapore (Wu et al., 2020). In the U.S., Hatcher et al. (2020) reported a hepatitis C-related mortality rate of 19.6% among American Indians and 5.9% among Asian Americans. According to WHO (2015), viral hepatitis caused approximately 1.34 million global deaths—more than TB and HIV. These deaths include 720,000 from cirrhosis and 470,000 from liver cancer. The mortality burden of viral hepatitis has grown by 22% since 2000, with 96% of hepatitis-related deaths resulting from long-term complications. Without widespread diagnosis and treatment, mortality will continue to rise.

Grossman's health capital model (1972, 2000, 2017) connects individual health status to

economic productivity and labor outcomes. It defines health and education as unique forms of capital that shape human capacity for work and earnings. Healthy individuals not only enjoy greater economic participation but also contribute more to national productivity.

Bloom and Canning (2000) identified four key pathways through which health improves productivity: 1) healthier individuals are more physically and mentally capable; 2) greater life expectancy encourages educational investment; 3) improved health promotes higher savings; and 4) healthier populations enjoy higher incomes and living standards.

In a projection study, Gountas et al. (2019) estimated that by 2030, Greece could see a 19.6% rise in HCV-related mortality, with direct and indirect costs reaching €2.3 billion and €1.1 billion, respectively. Eliminating HCV would require treating 90,000 individuals at an additional cost of €3.2–3.4 billion, with the cost per adjusted life-year lost ranging from €10,100 to €13,380

Study Design and Objectives

This study conducted an economic evaluation of the burden of hepatitis B and C in Pakistan. The objective was to estimate both direct and indirect costs associated with these infections, including productivity loss, absenteeism, employment outcomes, and foreign exchange impacts

Sampling Strategy

Given Pakistan's diverse geography and population, a multistage stratified cluster sampling technique was used to ensure representativeness and feasibility. In the first stage, the country was stratified by administrative regions, including Punjab, Sindh, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Balochistan, Islamabad Capital Territory, Gilgit-Baltistan, and Azad Jammu and Kashmir. A total of 70 districts out of 154 were randomly selected where public and private hepatitis treatment facilities were available. Within these districts, every third hepatitis B and every fifth hepatitis C patient aged between 5 and 75 years was selected if they were currently undergoing or had completed treatment between March 2023 and March 2025.

Absenteeism

Absenteeism was defined as the average number of sick days per month during the period of illness or treatment (Miroslav et al., 2017; Sajjad & Nosheen, 2022; Sajjad et al, 2024,2005).

Productivity Loss

Productivity losses were calculated as follows:

- **Hospitalized patients:** Hospital stay (days) × average daily income
- **Outpatients:** Visit days × average daily income (including caregiver) (Sajjad & Nosheen, 2022; Sajjad et al, 2024,2005).

Methods used:

- **Salary Conversion Method:** Estimates loss based on self-reported income.
- **Introspective Method:** Uses hypothetical scenarios based on survey responses.
- **Firm-Level Method:** Calculates losses using firm costs related to absenteeism and presenteeism (Baik et al., 2017; Khusro et al., 2015; Sajjad & Nosheen, 2022; Sajjad et al, 2024,2005).

Foreign Reserve Impact Estimation

To assess the economic cost in terms of foreign exchange depletion, the following formula was used:

$$FR = HBP*YC + HCP*YC$$

Foreign reserves = Total number of hepatitis B patients * average per patient diagnostic cost + total number of hepatitis c patients * average per patient diagnostic cost

Limitation of the above model

This model developed to include only per patient diagnostics expenses incurred. It did not incorporate with medication and treatment instruments because of lack of available data.

This estimate focuses solely on diagnostic expenses due to limited data on treatment costs (Sajjad & Nosheen, 2022).

Econometric Models

Model 1: Labor Mobility

To examine the effect of hepatitis on labor mobility (e.g., visa rejection), a logistic regression was estimated

$$\text{Labor mobility} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (\text{gender}) + \beta_2 (\text{age}) + \beta_3 (\text{marital status}) + \beta_4 (\text{sources of exposure}) + \beta_5 (\text{employment status}) + \beta_6 (\text{education}) + \varepsilon$$

In the equation the dependent variable is a dummy variable. It indicates the visa rejection a proxy of labor mobility and coded as “1” if the respondent’s visa is rejected due to hepatitis and “0” if the visa is not rejected due to hepatitis. Given the dichotomous dependent variable we estimated the equation (1) by using logistic regression.

Model 2: Absenteeism

To assess productivity loss through absenteeism, an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression was used

$$\text{Absenteeism} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (\text{gender}) + \beta_2 (\text{age}) + \beta_3 (\text{marital status}) + \beta_4 (\text{sources of exposure}) + \beta_5 (\text{employment status}) + \beta_6 (\text{education}) + \varepsilon$$

In the above equation, the dependent variable indicates the absenteeism during the treatment by the respondents exposed to the hepatitis. It is a continuous variable. the estimation was carried out by Ordinary Least Square (OLS) methodology.

Model 3: Employment Impact

To examine employment discrimination, the following logistic regression model was applied:

$$\text{Employment} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (\text{gender}) + \beta_2 (\text{age}) + \beta_3 (\text{marital status}) + \beta_4 (\text{sources of exposure}) + \beta_5 (\text{employment status}) + \beta_6 (\text{education}) + \varepsilon$$

The dependent variables in equation employment indicates that whether the respondent has been rejected from the job or not due to hepatitis. It is a dummy variable and coded as “1” if respondent has experienced rejection and “0” if there was no rejection

RESULTS AND THEIR INTERPRETATION Section I (a): Socio and Demographic analysis of the data

Gender of the Patient

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	3383	40.3	40.3	40.3
	Male	5005	59.7	59.7	100.0
	Total	8388	100.0	100.0	

The Table shows the frequency of male and female respondents of the current study. Out of total 8,388 hepatitis patients’ respondents the male respondents were 5,005 hepatitis patients and female were 3,383 with their respective ratio of 59.7% and 40.3%.

Age of the Patient

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	5-18 Years	305	3.6	3.6	3.6
	19-32 Years	2898	34.5	34.5	38.2
	33-46 Years	2721	32.4	32.4	70.6
	47-60 Years	1511	18.0	18.0	88.6
	>60 Years	953	11.4	11.4	100.0
	Total	8388	100.0	100.0	

Mean age with standard deviation

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation
Age of the Patient	8388	5	70	39.99	4.00	1.061
Valid N (listwise)	8388					

The above tables indicate the number of patients/respondents fall in a particular age group with their respective mean, median age and standard deviation. These tables explore that 3.6% of the patients lies in the age group 5-18 years and all of them are dependent as they are minor and not fall in working population whereas 34.5%, 32.4%, 18.0% and 11.4 % patients fall in age

group 19-32, 33-46, 47 -60 and above 60 years. The table also portrait that 84.9% of the patients were belong working population as the retirement age in Pakistan are 60 years and that 84.9% of patients lies in age group of 19 to 60 years. The mean and median age of respondents were estimated as 39.99 years and 40 years with standard deviation of 1.061.

Marital status

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Married	6709	80.0	80.0	80.0
	un married	1679	20.0	20.0	100.0
	Total	8388	100.0	100.0	

Table explains the material status of the patients/respondents. The statistics shows that 6709 (80%) of the respondents were married and the rest 1679 (20%) of the respondents were unmarried.

Geographical Regions

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	PUNJAB	4210	50.2	50.2	50.2
	Sindh	865	10.3	10.3	60.5
	GB	77	1.0	1.0	61.6
	KPK	2482	29.6	29.6	90.1
	Baluchistan	480	5.7	5.7	95.9
	AZAD Kashmir	149	1.8	1.8	97.6
	Islamabad Capital Territory	125	1.4	1.4	100.0
	Total	8388	100.0	100.0	

Cast/Race/Ethnicity

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Punjabi	2495	29.7	29.7	29.7
	Pashtun	2500	29.8	29.8	59.5
	Sindhi	1316	15.7	15.7	75.2
	Saraiki	1200	14.3	14.3	89.5
	Muhajir	201	2.4	2.4	91.9
	Hindko	450	5.3	5.3	97.2
	Chitrali	77	1.0	1.0	98.2
	KASHMIRI	149	1.8	1.8	100.0
	Total	8388	100.0	100.0	

The above Tables stats the caste and geographical region of the respondents. As the data was collected almost all corner of Pakistan, the major caste was mentioned in the questioner to highlight the geographical region of the patients. In the

table 5.4.1 the Saraiki caste represents the respondents from southern Punjab that are 14.3% of the total respondents whereas 29.7% are from other parts of Punjab. On the other side table 5.4 indicated that 50.4% of the respondents are from

Punjab whereas other table shows that 44% of the respondents are Punjabi. The difference of 6.4% respondents indicates the patients from other parts of the country travel towards Punjab for medication or the people migrated to Punjab for better employment opportunities or may be include both of them. The patients belong to Pashtuns and Hindko casts were geographically from Khyber Pakhtunkhwa weather residents of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa or any other parts of the country. The ratio of Hepatitis patients from

Khyber Pakhtunkhwa are estimated 35.1% (29.8% Pashtun + 5.3% Hindko's) of the total sample size whereas in table 5.4 it shows a ratio of 29.6%. The difference of 5.5% of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa people infected with either Hepatitis B or C were approach to other province of the country for hepatitis treatment or they were residents outside of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa or either includes both of them. Total of 480 (5.7%), 145 (1.8%) and 125 (1.4) of the patients were from Baluchistan, Azad Kashmir and Islamabad capital territory.

Number of patients Rusticated or Terminated due to Hepatitis B or C

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	112	1.3	1.3	1.3
	No	8276	98.7	98.7	100.0
	Total	8388	100.0	100.0	

The number employees rusticated from job and Job rejection because of Viral Hepatitis B or C were presented in table and table 5.17. Out of 8,388 hepatitis patients 112 (1.3%) respondents reported job loss/Rusticated due to viral Hepatitis B or C while 542 (6.5%) out of total 8388 respondents recorded their caused of job rejection because of Hepatitis.

Rejection from Job/ unemployment Caused by Viral Hepatitis B and C

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	542	6.5	6.5	6.5
	No	7846	93.5	93.5	100.0
	Total	8388	100.0	100.0	

tables concluded unemployment caused by viral hepatitis and an estimated 6.8% of the total unemployment was associated with viral hepatitis.

Number of patients reported Visa Rejection Due to Hepatitis

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	1239	14.8	14.8	14.8
	No	7149	85.2	85.2	100.0
	Total	8388	100.0	100.0	

Table determined the amount of total work visa rejected of Hepatitis patients. The figure showed that 14.8% (1239) patient's work visa was rejected based on viral Hepatitis infection. The people that can generate remittance for Pakistan was restricted to the country and caused unemployment.

Table 4.1.19 Total number of Patients sell their Assets for Treatment

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	1520	18.1	18.1	18.1
	No	6868	81.9	81.9	100.0
	Total	8388	100.0	100.0	
N	Valid				8388

Missing	0
Mean	1.82
Std. Deviation	.385

Table displayed the number of Hepatitis patients sell their assets to meet the pay the direct and indirect cost of treatment. The table showed that 18.1% of the patients sold some type of their assets and bear the expenditure associated to hepatitis B and C treatment. The sale of assets caused and increase in poverty in backward areas of the country.

Baseline estimation Labor mobility of hepatitis patients

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6	Model 7	Model 8	Model 9	Model 10
Male	0.033*** (0.008)	0.032*** (0.008)	0.032*** (0.008)	0.032*** (0.008)	0.030*** (0.008)	0.030*** (0.008)	0.030*** (0.008)	0.033*** (0.008)	0.033*** (0.008)	0.032*** (0.007)
Age of the Patient	-0.016*** (0.004)	-0.015*** (0.004)	-0.016*** (0.004)	-0.017*** (0.004)	-0.017*** (0.004)	-0.019*** (0.004)	-0.019*** (0.004)	-0.021*** (0.004)	-0.020*** (0.004)	-0.018*** (0.004)
Married	0.012 (0.010)	0.011 (0.010)	0.012 (0.010)	0.012 (0.010)	0.011 (0.010)	0.015 (0.009)	0.012 (0.009)	0.016* (0.009)	0.017* (0.009)	0.015 (0.009)
Dental clinic	-0.018 (0.013)	-0.022* (0.012)	-0.022* (0.012)	-0.026** (0.013)	-0.030** (0.013)	-0.030** (0.013)	-0.028** (0.013)	-0.021 (0.013)	-0.024* (0.013)	-0.030** (0.013)
Sexual relation	0.013 (0.047)	0.005 (0.046)	-0.000 (0.045)	0.001 (0.043)	-0.006 (0.040)	-0.018 (0.041)	-0.019 (0.041)	-0.025 (0.041)	-0.018 (0.044)	-0.016 (0.047)
Barber shop	-0.055** (0.026)	-0.052* (0.027)	-0.053* (0.027)	-0.055** (0.025)	-0.059** (0.023)	-0.068*** (0.020)	-0.070*** (0.019)	-0.078*** (0.017)	-0.076*** (0.018)	-0.077*** (0.019)
Beauty parlour	0.019 (0.027)	0.015 (0.026)	0.011 (0.025)	0.006 (0.025)	0.006 (0.025)	0.003 (0.025)	0.003 (0.025)	0.023 (0.026)	0.022 (0.025)	0.020 (0.025)
Surgery	0.011 (0.015)	0.008 (0.015)	0.006 (0.015)	-0.003 (0.015)	-0.002 (0.014)	-0.005 (0.014)	-0.007 (0.014)	0.005 (0.015)	0.004 (0.015)	-0.008 (0.014)
Blood transfusion	-0.016 (0.021)	-0.016 (0.021)	-0.019 (0.020)	-0.023 (0.020)	-0.019 (0.020)	-0.015 (0.020)	-0.017 (0.020)	-0.017 (0.021)	-0.016 (0.020)	-0.027 (0.019)
Vertical transmission	0.013 (0.012)	0.015 (0.012)	-0.001 (0.012)	-0.010 (0.011)	-0.010 (0.011)	-0.018* (0.011)	-0.019* (0.011)	-0.024** (0.010)	-0.027*** (0.010)	-0.025** (0.010)

Part time employee <30 hr/week	0.279*** (0.049)	0.262*** (0.047)	0.253*** (0.052)	0.273*** (0.049)	0.265*** (0.051)	0.226*** (0.050)	0.213*** (0.050)	0.252*** (0.053)	0.269*** (0.056)	0.257*** (0.053)
Self employee	0.151*** (0.012)	0.156*** (0.011)	0.160*** (0.011)	0.153*** (0.011)	0.165*** (0.011)	0.163*** (0.011)	0.165*** (0.010)	0.162*** (0.011)	0.140*** (0.012)	0.146*** (0.011)
Dependent	-0.016 (0.010)	-0.013 (0.010)	-0.011 (0.010)	-0.014 (0.010)	0.001 (0.009)	0.001 (0.009)	0.003 (0.009)	-0.001 (0.009)	-0.018* (0.011)	-0.013 (0.010)
Retired	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)	0.000 (.)
un-employed	0.747*** (0.036)	0.741*** (0.036)	0.740*** (0.035)	0.686*** (0.043)	0.703*** (0.042)	0.765*** (0.042)	0.745*** (0.045)	0.755*** (0.052)	0.728*** (0.053)	0.674*** (0.059)
Education and Awareness	0.058*** (0.004)	0.058*** (0.004)	0.060*** (0.004)	0.059*** (0.004)	0.056*** (0.004)	0.058*** (0.004)	0.058*** (0.004)	0.054*** (0.004)	0.057*** (0.004)	0.062*** (0.004)
Total number of Family Members		-0.023*** (0.006)	-0.028*** (0.006)	-0.021*** (0.005)	-0.020*** (0.005)	-0.016*** (0.005)	-0.019*** (0.005)	-0.024*** (0.005)	-0.025*** (0.005)	-0.014*** (0.005)
Number of Infected Family Members			0.038*** (0.005)	0.025*** (0.005)	0.029*** (0.005)	0.030*** (0.005)	0.032*** (0.005)	0.034*** (0.005)	0.035*** (0.005)	0.037*** (0.005)
Death of a Family member				0.084*** (0.007)	0.071*** (0.008)	0.071*** (0.007)	0.067*** (0.007)	0.059*** (0.007)	0.055*** (0.007)	0.050*** (0.007)
Complete health insurance					0.116*** (0.026)	0.107*** (0.025)	0.094*** (0.024)	0.091*** (0.024)	0.114*** (0.025)	0.101*** (0.023)
Estimated Direct Medical Cost per Month						-0.089***	-0.113***	-0.094***	-0.084***	-0.074***

						(0.010)	(0.013)	(0.014)	(0.014)	(0.013)
Estimate Indirect Medical Cost per Month							0.061***	0.065***	0.075***	0.075***
							(0.013)	(0.012)	(0.011)	(0.010)
Total Cost Spent on Treatment								-0.054***	-0.051***	-0.062***
								(0.007)	(0.007)	(0.007)
Monthly Income									-0.037***	-0.036***
									(0.004)	(0.004)
Total Cost of Visit Per Month										-0.025***
										(0.003)
Observations	8331	8331	8331	8331	8331	8331	8331	8331	8331	8331

This table presents the marginal effects of Logit regressions examining the effects of hepatitis on labor mobility. Standard errors (in brackets) are robust to arbitrary heteroskedasticity. *, **, and *** indicate statistical significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% level, respectively.

Logistic regression analysis is conducted to assess how hepatitis infections influence labor mobility, proxied through visa rejection as a binary dependent variable (1 = visa rejected, 0 = not rejected). The average marginal effects from the 10 model specifications reveal key patterns: The average marginal effects are estimated by taking labor mobility as dichotomous variable i.e., 1 (if an individual's visa is rejected) and "0" (if an individual's not rejected).

The "average marginal effects" derived from logistic regression provide more holistic picture of regression phenomenon to compare outcomes. On average, for male are 3.2 percent significantly more chances of visa rejection, as compared with female respondent. Column (10) indicates 1.8 percentage significantly lower probability (less likely) with an additional year of age that visa would be rejected.

The above table explored that male patients face significantly higher visa rejection probabilities than females, with a marginal effect of 0.032 ($p < 0.01$), whereas patient of the age found that a one-year increase in age decreases the likelihood of visa rejection by approximately 1.8 percentage points, holding other factors constant. - Source of

Exposure: Infection through dental clinics (-3%), barber shops (-7.7%), and vertical transmission (-2.5%) is associated with significantly lower probabilities of visa rejection. - Employment Status: Being a part-time worker (+25.7%), self-employed (+14.6%), or unemployed (+67.4%) significantly increases the likelihood of visa rejection due to hepatitis. - Household Characteristics: Larger family size is associated with a 1.4% lower chance of visa rejection. A higher estimated direct medical cost per month also reduces visa rejection probability (-7.4%). - Positive Predictors: Greater education and awareness (+6.2%), number of infected family members (+3.7%), death of a family member (+5%), and complete health insurance (+10.1%) are all significantly associated with higher visa rejection likelihood. - Economic Burden: Higher total cost of treatment, monthly income, and cost of medical visits all increase the odds of visa rejection. These results highlight how hepatitis B and C significantly influence cross-border labor mobility, especially among males, unemployed individuals, and those bearing high treatment-related costs

Baseline estimation Absenteeism of Hepatitis B and C patients during treatment (labor productivity)

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6	Model 7	Model 8	Model 9	Model 10
Male	0.015*	0.016**	0.016**	0.016**	0.017**	0.017**	0.017**	0.020**	0.020**	0.025***
	(0.008)	(0.008)	(0.008)	(0.008)	(0.008)	(0.008)	(0.008)	(0.008)	(0.008)	(0.007)
Age of the Patient	0.011**	0.009**	0.008*	0.008*	0.008*	0.007*	0.007	0.005	0.004	-0.002
	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)
Married	-0.044***	-0.041***	-0.039***	-0.039***	-0.038***	-0.037***	-0.038***	-0.034***	-0.034***	-0.025**
	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.010)
Dental clinic	-0.053***	-0.048***	-0.050***	-0.049***	-0.048***	-0.047***	-0.047***	-0.034**	-0.034**	-0.013
	(0.014)	(0.014)	(0.014)	(0.014)	(0.014)	(0.014)	(0.014)	(0.015)	(0.015)	(0.014)
Sexual relation	0.055*	0.060**	0.054*	0.053*	0.060**	0.057**	0.059**	0.052*	0.051*	0.059**
	(0.028)	(0.029)	(0.028)	(0.028)	(0.029)	(0.029)	(0.029)	(0.028)	(0.028)	(0.029)
Barber shop	0.070***	0.065**	0.066***	0.067***	0.070***	0.068***	0.064***	0.050**	0.047*	0.035
	(0.025)	(0.025)	(0.025)	(0.025)	(0.024)	(0.025)	(0.025)	(0.025)	(0.025)	(0.025)
Beauty parlour	-0.025	-0.023	-0.028	-0.025	-0.027	-0.027	-0.025	-0.007	-0.006	0.001
	(0.029)	(0.029)	(0.029)	(0.029)	(0.029)	(0.028)	(0.028)	(0.029)	(0.028)	(0.029)
Surgery	-0.034**	-0.030*	-0.033**	-0.031**	-0.031**	-0.032**	-0.033**	-0.020	-0.019	0.025*
	(0.016)	(0.016)	(0.016)	(0.016)	(0.016)	(0.016)	(0.016)	(0.016)	(0.016)	(0.015)
Blood transfusion	-0.047**	-0.049**	-0.052**	-0.050**	-0.054**	-0.052**	-0.052**	-0.049**	-0.049**	-0.019
	(0.023)	(0.023)	(0.023)	(0.023)	(0.023)	(0.022)	(0.022)	(0.022)	(0.022)	(0.021)
Vertical transmission	0.033***	0.030***	0.017	0.019*	0.019*	0.016	0.015	0.007	0.008	-0.006
	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.011)	(0.011)	(0.011)	(0.011)	(0.011)	(0.011)	(0.011)	(0.010)
Part time employee <30 hr/week	0.204***	0.212***	0.210***	0.207***	0.201***	0.184***	0.180***	0.201***	0.205***	0.200***

	(0.028)	(0.029)	(0.025)	(0.024)	(0.025)	(0.024)	(0.025)	(0.027)	(0.027)	(0.029)
Self employee	0.098***	0.089***	0.091***	0.093***	0.077***	0.072***	0.074***	0.068***	0.081***	0.047***
	(0.014)	(0.014)	(0.014)	(0.014)	(0.015)	(0.015)	(0.015)	(0.015)	(0.015)	(0.015)
Dependent	0.017	0.010	0.010	0.010	-0.007	-0.012	-0.009	-0.018	-0.006	-0.035**
	(0.013)	(0.014)	(0.014)	(0.014)	(0.014)	(0.014)	(0.014)	(0.014)	(0.014)	(0.015)
Retired	0.097***	0.082***	0.074***	0.096***	0.071***	0.064***	0.065***	0.086***	0.082***	0.104***
	(0.014)	(0.015)	(0.017)	(0.017)	(0.018)	(0.018)	(0.018)	(0.020)	(0.021)	(0.021)
un-employed	-0.103**	-0.099**	-0.106**	-0.084*	-0.103**	-0.097*	-0.106**	-0.127**	-0.114**	0.017
	(0.050)	(0.051)	(0.048)	(0.049)	(0.049)	(0.050)	(0.050)	(0.052)	(0.052)	(0.048)
Education and Awareness	0.045***	0.046***	0.046***	0.046***	0.048***	0.048***	0.047***	0.042***	0.040***	0.023***
	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.003)
Total number of Family Members		0.031***	0.026***	0.025***	0.024***	0.024***	0.020***	0.014**	0.013**	-0.023***
		(0.007)	(0.007)	(0.007)	(0.007)	(0.007)	(0.007)	(0.007)	(0.007)	(0.007)
Number of Infected Family Members			0.037***	0.042***	0.039***	0.040***	0.041***	0.037***	0.037***	0.027***
			(0.007)	(0.007)	(0.007)	(0.007)	(0.007)	(0.007)	(0.007)	(0.007)
Death of a Family member				-0.033***	-0.024**	-0.024**	-0.022**	-0.025***	-0.024**	0.005
				(0.009)	(0.009)	(0.009)	(0.009)	(0.009)	(0.009)	(0.009)
Complete health insurance					-0.092***	-0.093***	-0.100***	-0.112***	-0.117***	-0.071***
					(0.021)	(0.021)	(0.021)	(0.020)	(0.020)	(0.020)
Estimated Direct Medical Cost per Month						-0.051***	-0.070***	-0.043***	-0.047***	-0.049***
						(0.012)	(0.015)	(0.015)	(0.015)	(0.014)

Estimate Indirect Medical Cost per Month							0.056***	0.055***	0.054***	0.016
							(0.019)	(0.019)	(0.019)	(0.017)
Total Cost Spent on Treatment								-0.059***	-0.061***	-0.002
								(0.008)	(0.009)	(0.009)
Monthly Income									0.016***	0.009
									(0.006)	(0.006)
Total Cost of Visit Per Month										0.100***
										(0.005)
Constant	1.753***	1.674***	1.633***	1.632***	1.651***	1.758***	1.697***	1.825***	1.796***	1.624***
	(0.024)	(0.030)	(0.030)	(0.030)	(0.030)	(0.040)	(0.044)	(0.045)	(0.046)	(0.045)
Observations	8388	8388	8388	8388	8388	8388	8388	8388	8388	8388

Notes: This table presents the results of OLS regressions examining the effects of hepatitis on labor productivity. Standard errors (in brackets) are robust to arbitrary heteroscedasticity. *, **, and *** indicate statistical significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% level, respectively.

This section explores the effect of hepatitis on absenteeism, an indirect indicator of reduced labor productivity, using OLS regression. The above figure explored the results of OLS regression models estimated for the effect of Hepatitis B and C on absenteeism from job based on gender of the patient, age of the patients, material status, source of exposure, employment status, family size, direct and indirect cost and monthly income of the infect person's family. The above figure model 10 showed significant effect of gender on absenteeism/productivity and found that male patient significantly high probability of absenteeism than female. The magnitude of male patients indicated 25% greater probability of absenteeism than female whereas on average age of the patient has also direct impact on absenteeism (productivity). Material status of the patient and source of exposure of Hepatitis B and C were found indirectly related to absenteeism from job of employees with hepatitis B or C virus, the probability of married Patients of Hepatitis B or C were found 44% less than unmarried while patients exposed for hepatitis from dental clinic,

beauty parlor, surgery and blood transfusion had on average had significant indirect impact on absenteeism while the effect sexual relation and vertical transmission with absenteeism were found directly. The results of OLS model also indicated the significant direct effect of employment status of Viral Hepatitis patients on absenteeism, the probability of absenteeism among part time employee, self-employed and retired employees were estimated 29%, 47% and 10.4% respectively while the effect of unemployed and dependent patients were estimated significantly indirect to absenteeism. The results also revealed that family size and number of infect family members were also significant direct impact of absenteeism and found on average 22% and 37% respectively whereas the effect of complete health insurance was estimated indirect with absenteeism due to hepatitis infection. The estimated results of direct medical cost, Indirect medical cost and monthly income of the patients also explored the direct impact of viral hepatitis infection on absenteeism from job among hepatitis patients.

Baseline estimation Job rejection of Hepatitis B and C patients

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6	Model 7	Model 8	Model 9	Model 10
Male	0.015*** (0.005)	0.015*** (0.005)	0.015*** (0.005)	0.013** (0.005)	0.011** (0.005)	0.012** (0.005)	0.012** (0.005)	0.014*** (0.005)	0.014*** (0.005)	0.013*** (0.005)
Age of the Patient	-0.001 (0.003)	-0.000 (0.003)	-0.000 (0.003)	-0.001 (0.003)	-0.001 (0.003)	-0.002 (0.003)	-0.002 (0.003)	-0.003 (0.003)	-0.003 (0.003)	-0.001 (0.003)
Married	-0.007 (0.008)	-0.008 (0.008)	-0.008 (0.008)	-0.009 (0.008)	-0.010 (0.008)	-0.007 (0.007)	-0.007 (0.007)	-0.005 (0.007)	-0.004 (0.007)	-0.007 (0.007)
Dental clinic	-0.011 (0.009)	-0.015* (0.008)	-0.015* (0.008)	-0.016* (0.008)	-0.021** (0.008)	-0.020** (0.008)	-0.021** (0.008)	-0.019** (0.008)	-0.021** (0.008)	-0.022*** (0.008)
Sexual relation	0.108*** (0.040)	0.099** (0.039)	0.099** (0.039)	0.102*** (0.037)	0.081*** (0.029)	0.073** (0.030)	0.072** (0.028)	0.064** (0.026)	0.065** (0.026)	0.062** (0.025)
Barber shop	0.023 (0.029)	0.025 (0.032)	0.025 (0.032)	0.020 (0.028)	0.011 (0.026)	0.005 (0.025)	0.006 (0.026)	0.000 (0.024)	0.000 (0.025)	0.002 (0.028)
Beauty parlour	-0.012 (0.016)	-0.013 (0.015)	-0.013 (0.015)	-0.020 (0.014)	-0.018 (0.014)	-0.022* (0.013)	-0.023* (0.013)	-0.008 (0.017)	-0.009 (0.016)	-0.012 (0.015)
Surgery	0.008 (0.012)	0.006 (0.012)	0.006 (0.012)	0.000 (0.011)	0.002 (0.011)	0.004 (0.011)	0.004 (0.011)	0.009 (0.012)	0.008 (0.012)	-0.005 (0.010)
Blood transfusion	-0.014 (0.012)	-0.013 (0.013)	-0.013 (0.013)	-0.014 (0.012)	-0.008 (0.013)	-0.008 (0.013)	-0.008 (0.013)	-0.011 (0.013)	-0.010 (0.013)	-0.017 (0.012)
Vertical transmission	0.005 (0.008)	0.007 (0.009)	0.008 (0.009)	0.001 (0.008)	0.001 (0.008)	-0.003 (0.008)	-0.003 (0.008)	-0.007 (0.007)	-0.008 (0.007)	-0.006 (0.007)
Part time employee <30 hr/week	0.095***	0.079***	0.079***	0.095***	0.087***	0.072***	0.076***	0.121***	0.123***	0.110***

	(0.030)	(0.028)	(0.028)	(0.029)	(0.029)	(0.023)	(0.025)	(0.030)	(0.031)	(0.027)
Self employee	0.000 (0.013)	0.007 (0.012)	0.007 (0.012)	-0.002 (0.012)	0.020** (0.009)	0.018** (0.009)	0.017* (0.009)	0.016* (0.009)	0.005 (0.010)	0.015* (0.008)
Dependent	-0.053*** (0.011)	-0.048*** (0.010)	-0.048*** (0.010)	-0.053*** (0.011)	-0.028*** (0.009)	-0.027*** (0.009)	-0.027*** (0.009)	-0.028*** (0.008)	-0.036*** (0.010)	-0.029*** (0.008)
Retired	0.000 (.)									
un-employed	0.512*** (0.040)	0.494*** (0.045)	0.495*** (0.045)	0.374*** (0.053)	0.421*** (0.049)	0.466*** (0.055)	0.481*** (0.054)	0.442*** (0.068)	0.424*** (0.062)	0.310*** (0.053)
Education and Awareness	0.030*** (0.003)	0.030*** (0.003)	0.030*** (0.003)	0.030*** (0.003)	0.025*** (0.003)	0.026*** (0.003)	0.026*** (0.003)	0.025*** (0.003)	0.026*** (0.003)	0.032*** (0.003)
Total number of Family Members		-0.021*** (0.005)	-0.020*** (0.005)	-0.013*** (0.004)	-0.010*** (0.004)	-0.008** (0.004)	-0.007** (0.004)	-0.009** (0.004)	-0.010*** (0.004)	-0.002 (0.003)
Number of Infected Family Members			-0.001 (0.004)	-0.010** (0.004)	-0.003 (0.004)	-0.001 (0.003)	-0.001 (0.003)	0.002 (0.004)	0.003 (0.004)	0.005 (0.003)
Death of a Family member				0.053*** (0.004)	0.036*** (0.004)	0.034*** (0.004)	0.035*** (0.004)	0.029*** (0.004)	0.028*** (0.004)	0.023*** (0.004)
Complete health insurance					0.134*** (0.020)	0.131*** (0.019)	0.136*** (0.020)	0.135*** (0.020)	0.148*** (0.021)	0.127*** (0.018)
Estimated Direct Medical Cost per Month						-0.038*** (0.007)	-0.032*** (0.009)	-0.018 (0.011)	-0.013 (0.010)	-0.009 (0.008)
Estimate Indirect Medical Cost per Month							-0.013	-0.014	-0.012	-0.009

							(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.008)
Total Cost Spent on Treatment								-0.034***	-0.032***	-0.035***
								(0.006)	(0.006)	(0.005)
Monthly Income									-0.013***	-0.010***
									(0.003)	(0.003)
Total Cost of Visit Per Month										-0.020***
										(0.002)
Observations	8331	8331	8331	8331	8331	8331	8331	8331	8331	8331

This table presents the marginal effects of Logit regressions examining the effects of hepatitis on employment. Standard errors (in brackets) are robust to arbitrary heteroskedasticity. *, **, and *** indicate statistical significance at the 10%, 5% and 1% level, respectively.

The objective of this estimation approach is to estimate the impact of hepatitis B and C on job rejection. We have empirically estimated equation (3) by using logistics regression econometric techniques. Figure 4.10 contains outcome for equation (3) and presented the average marginal effect from logistics regression for the probability of job rejection restricted to wide range of independent variables included in the current study. The average marginal effects were estimated by taking job rejection because of hepatitis infection as dichotomous variable i.e., 1 (if an individual's experienced job rejection caused by hepatitis B or C) and "0" (if an individual's experienced job rejection caused by hepatitis B or C). The results of "average marginal effects" derived from logistic regression provide more complete picture of regression phenomenon to compare outcomes. On average, for male are 1.5 percent significantly more chances of experienced job rejection caused by hepatitis B or C, as compared with female respondent. Column (10) indicates 1% significantly lower probability (less likely) with an additional year of age that job be rejected due hepatitis B or C.

The result indicates that respondents who exposed to hepatitis B or C from dental clinic, barber shop and Blood transfusion found to be 3, 7.7 and 2.7 percent less likely to be rejected for job respectively. Furthermore, figure 4.10 showed that respondents working as part time employee, self-employee and unemployed have 9.5, 1.5 and 5.12 percent significantly higher probability (more likely) for experienced job rejection caused by hepatitis B or C. The household size and Estimated Direct Medical Cost and indirect medical costs per month were estimated to be significant negative effect on experienced job rejection caused by hepatitis B or C and significantly lower probability (less likely) with an additional year. the estimated average probability of household size and direct medical cost and indirect medical costs -0.008 with P-value of 0.004 and -0.018 with P-value of 0.011 and -0.012 with P-value of 0.008 indicated that probability of significantly lower probability (less likely) with job rejection caused by hepatitis B or C. Monthly income of the patients and their family was also found indirect effect and significantly lower probability (less likely) with job rejection caused by hepatitis B or C.

Conclusion

This study underscores the profound socioeconomic burden imposed by Hepatitis B and C in Pakistan, particularly in terms of labor market outcomes and productivity losses. The findings reveal that viral hepatitis significantly reduces labor mobility, increases absenteeism, and contributes to economic vulnerability through job loss and asset depletion for medical treatment. These impacts not only threaten individual livelihoods but also hinder national economic growth by diminishing the productive capacity of the workforce.

The study further highlights the urgent need for targeted public health interventions, expanded screening programs, and access to affordable treatment. Integrating hepatitis control into broader economic and labor market policies is essential to mitigate its adverse effects and promote sustainable development. Addressing this silent epidemic is not only a public health imperative but also a critical step toward achieving inclusive economic progress in Pakistan.

The regression estimates across the three dimensions—visa rejection, absenteeism, and job rejection—highlight the substantial labor market costs of Hepatitis B and C in Pakistan. Gender disparities, exposure channels, employment type, household structure, and financial capacity all condition the degree of labor market disadvantage. These findings underscore the need for policy reforms that protect infected individuals from discrimination and improve access to medical care, insurance, and job retention support.

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